

TAJ
MADIKERI RESORT & SPA
COORG

April 18,2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. Aditya Prabhu H** student of **Srinivas University College of Hotel Management & Tourism, Mangalore** had undergone his **Industrial Exposure Training** in Food Production, Food & Beverage Services ,Front Office & Housekeeping Department at the **Taj Madikeri Resort & Spa, Coorg** from **December 13, 2021 to April 17,2022**.

During the period of training, he was found to be good & sincere.

We wish him all the best in his future endeavors.

For **Taj Madikeri Resort & Spa, Coorg**
(a Unit of Kaveri Retreats & Resorts LTD.)

Satya NVV
Human Resources Manager

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